

Fabrication of Mesoporous TiO₂ Electrode with Sawdust (Ironwood) Organic Dye Sensitized Solar Cell

Htet Htet Nwe¹, Than Than Win² and Yin Maung Maung³

Abstract

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) powder was operated by using ball-milling for 20 h to reduce particle size and it was meshed with 3-stage mesh sieves (100 mesh, 250 mesh, 400 mesh) to get uniform particle size. The TiO₂ powder was confirmed by FESEM (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope) and XRD (X-ray Diffraction) analysis. FESEM revealed that TiO₂ powder exhibited mesoporous structure. The XRD indicated the anatase phase of TiO₂ powder with tetragonal structure. (1×1 inch²) ITO/glasses worked as transparent substrates and TiO₂ paste was deposited onto glass substrate by rolling with glass rod. The different weights of sawdust dye were used for the photosensitizer and UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to examine the optical properties of sawdust dye solution. TiO₂ film was sensitized with different weights of sawdust dye solution. ITO/glass substrate for counter electrode was filled with carbon by using oil heater. Both films were offset together with binder clips and a few drops of iodine was added between them. The photovoltaic properties of Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSCs) were measured under illumination condition. The experimental findings resulted from this research work can be of great help for low-cost and Eco-friendly DSSC application.

Key words: Mesoporous TiO₂, DSSC, Ironwood sawdust, FESEM, XRD

Introduction

A dye-sensitized solar cell is a low-cost solar cell belonging to the group of thin film solar cells. It is based on a semiconductor formed between a photo-sensitized anode and an electrolyte, a photoelectrochemical system. A later version of a dye solar cell, also known as the Grätzel cell, was invented in 1991 by Michael Grätzel and Brian O'Regan (1991). Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) have aroused much attention as a cheap and next generation solar cell. It is well known that a typical dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC) consists of porous TiO₂ film, dye molecules which are sensitive to sunlight, and an organic liquid electrolyte, essentially containing iodide and triiodide ions as a redox couple (Lin et al, 2011 & Wei et al, 2011). These three layers are sandwiched together between two conducting glasses, one covered with a thin layer of TiO₂ and the other with a platinum layer. DSSCs show considerable potential as a relatively low-cost alternative to silicon based solar cells (Tsai et al, 2011). In general, the porous semiconductor film consists of a large collection of nano-sized particles of a metal oxide interconnected by meso-sized pores, deposited onto the conductive surface of a transparent electrode. This porous metal oxide film acts as a high surface area support for the sensitizer, a pathway for electrical current and a porous membrane for diffusion of the redox couple. The high surface area of the nanocrystalline TiO₂ film plays a crucial role in increasing the performance of the photoelectrochemical cell in energy conversion (Park et al, 2008). Therefore, mesoporous TiO₂ are expected to facilitate pore diffusion, give easier access to the film surface, and allow the nano crystal junctions to be formed under better control (Hou et al, 2005). In addition, the inorganic/organic sol will be freely and easily coated on the whole surface of the TCO, which may lead to superior interfacial contact properties with TCO (Ahn et al, 2007).

Experimental

Substrate Preparation

ITO/glass slides (1" x 1") were used as transparent substrates. Firstly, ITO/glass slides were cleaned in HCl:HNO₃ solution for 15 minutes and immersed in ethanol and DIW for three times. After that, they were dried at room temperature. Both sides of ITO/glass slides

¹Dr., Demonstrator, Department of Physics, Dagon University

²Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, University of Yangon

³Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Physics, Kyaing Tong University

were identified for conductivity by using multimeter. Non-conductive sides of the ITO/glass slides were marked and other sides were used for photoelectrode and counter electrode.

TiO₂ Paste

Analar grade TiO₂ powder was operated by ball-milling for 20 h to reduce particle size and sieved with 3-stage mesh sieves (100 mesh, 250 mesh, 400 mesh) to get uniform particle size. Structural and phase assignment of TiO₂ powder was examined by XRD. From the XRD result, TiO₂ performs anatase phase with the crystallized size of 37 nm. The XRD pattern of TiO₂ powder was mentioned in Fig 1. The powder was also confirmed by FESEM and the result showed that TiO₂ powder has mesoporous structure. The average grain size and pore size were 30 nm and 50 nm respectively. The FESEM photograph of TiO₂ powder was shown in Fig 2. 10 g of TiO₂ mesoporous powder was put in the mortar and mixed with 20 g of acetic acid. The mixture was grinded by pestle to be uniform colloidal paste. TiO₂ paste was allowed to set for 1 h at a room temperature to get better paste.

Figure 1. XRD pattern of TiO₂ powder

Figure 2. FESEM photo of mesoporous TiO₂ powder

Mesoporous TiO₂ Photoelectrode

In order to obtain mesoporous TiO₂ electrode, (0.6×0.8 inch²) dimension on conductive side of ITO/glass substrate was holed by using scotch tape. TiO₂ paste was coated onto ITO/glass substrate by sliding up and down with glass rod. The film was dried at 450 °C for 1 h. Eventually, it could be used as photoelectrode.

Dye Solution

Different weights of sawdust (Ironwood) [10 g, 15 g & 20 g] were measured and dissolved in 100 ml of DIW. The mixture was stirred thoroughly and set for 1 day to get red-black coloured solution. The mixture was then filtered and heated at 110 °C for 30 min. It was placed at room temperature for 3 days for the best result. Finally, it was ready to use for dye sensitizer. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to examine the optical properties of sawdust dye solution. Fig 3 showed UV-Vis spectroscopy result for different weights of dye solution. Table 1 indicated that the UV-Vis ranges and their absorbance. From the results, it was found that sawdust dye solution with different weights could absorb UV and visible light. The maximum absorption of dye solution with different weights was 4 while minimum absorbance was 2.7.

Counter Electrode

The conductive side of ITO/glass substrate was also holed with the same dimension of TiO₂ electrode and filled with carbon to the entire hole of the slide in order not to miss any spots by using oil heater. And then, the film was heated at 100 °C for 30 min.

Table 1. UV-Vis range, absorbance and pH for different weights of sawdust dyes

Weight (g)	Light range (nm)	Absorbance	pH
10	190 ~ 400	3.9 ~ 4.0	5.5
15	190 ~ 410	2.7 ~ 4.0	5.4
20	200 ~ 410	4.0	5.6

Figure 3. UV-Vis spectrum for different weights of sawdust dye solution

Dye Sensitized Solar Cell

The entire film except TiO₂ paste coated area was covered with scotch tape and placed in dye solution for 1 h. The TiO₂ film was dried at room temperature. And then, the TiO₂ electrode was faced down and the counter electrode was faced up so that the conductive sides were facing each other. Both films were offset together by binder clips. A few drops of iodine was added between them by capillary action. The offset edges became the contact points for the positive and negative electrodes. Finally, photovoltaic properties of DSSC were measured by using voltmeter and ammeter under illumination. The flow diagram of preparation for DSSC was indicated in Fig 4.

Figure 4. Flow diagram of preparation for DSSC

Photovoltaic Properties of DSSC

The photovoltaic properties of mesoporous TiO₂ electrode with sawdust (Pyinkado) organic dye were defined by parameters such as short-circuit current (I_{sc}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) obtained under illumination. Fig 5 (a-c) showed the change in photocurrent as a function of voltage of TiO₂ electrode with different weights of sawdust (Ironwood) organic dye. The important parameters such as conversion efficiency and fill factor were evaluated and indicated in Table 2.

Figure 5. Photocurrent-voltage curves of TiO₂ DSSC with (a) 10 g; (b) 15 g; and (c) 20 g of organic dye

Table 2. Solar cell parameters of DSSC with organic dye at different weights

Weight [g]	I_m [mA cm ⁻²]	V_m [mV]	I_{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{oc} [mV]	Efficiency [%]	Fill factor
10	0.47	34.00	0.55	49.40	1.20	0.59
15	0.51	41.80	0.65	57.00	1.60	0.58
20	0.61	42.00	0.71	58.77	1.92	0.61

Conclusion

The DSSC of mesoporous TiO₂ photoelectrode with different weights of organic sawdust dye have been successfully fabricated. As a result of XRD, the TiO₂ powder was observed to be anatase structure with the crystallite size of 37 nm. According to FESEM result, TiO₂ powder exhibited mesoporous structure. The average grain size and pore size were measured to be 30 nm and 50 nm, respectively. The result from UV-Vis spectroscopy revealed that different weights of sawdust dyes could absorb both UV and visible light. Thus, the sawdust (Ironwood) was said to be quite promising candidate for natural dye sensitizer. From the I-V graph, it was found that the efficiency of TiO₂ electroded DSSC with (20 g) organic dye was the highest efficiency and it was 1.92 %. It is also found that the fabricated DSSCs will be a significant step towards the development of low-cost and Eco-friendly DSSC application.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Professor Dr Win Win Thar, Head of Department of Physics, Dagon University for her kind permission to carry out this study. We are also grateful to Professor Dr May Myint Si, Department of Physics, Dagon University.

References

- Ahn, K.S., *et al*, (2007), *J. App. Phys.*, **101**, 084312
 Hou, K., *et al*, (2005), *J. Mater. Chem.*, **15**, 2414
 Lin, L.Y., *et al*, (2011), *J. Power Sources*, **196**, 1671
 Park, K.H., *et al*, (2008), *J. Adv. Eng. & Tech.*, **1**(1), 27
 Regan, B.O. and Grätzel, M., (1991), *Nature*, **353**(6346), 737
 Tsai, T. H., *et al*, (2011), *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, **6**, 3333
 Wei, Z., *et al*, (2011), *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, **6**, 1871